

Paper 6
**STUDY ON SOFT SKILL TRAINING AND
DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME FOR MANAGEMENT
STUDENTS**

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Abstract:

The higher education in India as well as the market scenario and requirement is changing very fast and moving ahead due to stiff competition. A decade ago, those individuals who had a brilliant academic record with added work experience were well sought after by most of the corporate institutions with a fixed range of pay as remuneration. But today hard skills and experience are not sufficient enough for the way in and growth in the corporate world. Employers prefer to hire and promote those persons who are resourceful, ethical, and self directed and motivated with good communication and soft skills. Shortage of soft skills in the candidates has resulted in low hiring by corporate. Corporate giants have also made its point clear regarding soft skills training programme to be included in the management courses and will surely have a positive overall development in the course.

In spite of such immense significance of soft skills, many management colleges are hesitant to incorporate soft skills training in the curriculum of management courses. This paper is based on the improvement training and development programme has on the students regularly exposed to soft skills sessions, activities and those who are deprived of the same.

Keywords: Soft skills, Soft skills training programme

INTRODUCTION

The education scenario in the recent times is changing very fast. No matter how well equipped an individual think he is with respect to the technical skills he will not get success in the corporate world. Communication skill is an important soft skills element and plays an important task in the business world.

Soft skills have become a crucial and increasingly sort after quality for careers in corporate world, irrespective of the sector. Requirement of soft skills in a job has made the competition for job acquisition and job sustainability tougher. All those candidates who wish to get an edge over their competitor are expected to improve their soft skills so that they will be able to come out as

a winner irrespective of the hurdles that they face in the employment procedure. The global competitiveness of Indian industry and also its employment generation potential is clearly dependent on availability of required skills and trained personnel. Soft skills are different and distinct from Hard Skills .Soft skills are those skills that add more significance to the hard skills ornamented by an individual.

Soft skills are perceived as those capabilities that inherent in an individual. These competencies exist in every individual a particular level. But if these skills are not used or if the individual who adorns these skills. Individual is unaware of it then that individual will never be able to utilize his / her inherent skills.

DEFINITION

Soft skills are essentially people's skills or personality specific skills. According to Hewitt Sean (2008) soft skills are "non-technical, intangible, personality specific skills" which determines an individual's strength as "a leader, listener and negotiator, or as a conflict mediator". Soft skills are the traits and abilities of attitude and behaviour rather than of knowledge or technical aptitude.

OBJECTIVE OF SOFT SKILLS TRAINING PROGRAMMES

The main objectives of the soft skills training imparted to MBA students should be to:

1. To develop communication skills (spoken and written).
2. To identify the skills required to perform up to the standards in interview.
3. Make the student capable with respect to the current Job requirements, by expanding the skills set.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Method: Data collected for the research topic is from secondary sources.

CORE ELEMENTS IN SOFT SKILL

1. FORMAL HANDSHAKE

First impression is formed while an interaction between two individuals happen and handshake is the first point of contact. There are important fundamentals to remember when having a formal handshake.

ESSENTIAL POINTS FOR GOOD FORMAL HANDSHAKE

1. Maintain a good eye to eye contact with the other person.
2. Smile when a formal handshake is done.
3. Have a firm grip but don't crush the other person's hand.

4. Be confident and introduce yourself to the other person.
5. Leave the hand after few seconds of handshake.
6. In a handshake with lady. The lady has offer for a handshake first.

2. GROUP DISCUSSION

Presenting the different ideas on a particular topic in a systematic way and also listening to the others when points are made differentiates the individuals who attend a group discussion and aim for employment and the end of the day. A standard group discussion happens for 10 to 12 minutes with 8 to 10 members participating.

There is key area in a group discussion which the company look for and judge while selecting the candidates. The number of individuals selected for future process based on the vacancy in the organization.

POINTS TO REMEMBER FOR GROUP DISCUSSION

1. Keep eye to eye contact while speaking.
2. Initiate the Group Discussion and also allow others to speak
3. Speak clearly and use facts and figures relating to topic to justify
4. Make sure to bring the discussion on track
5. Positive attitude
6. Listen carefully to others (important quality to become a good manager)
7. Formal dressing

QUALITY'S JUDGED IN GROUP DISCUSSION

1. How good is the communication with others
2. Behaviour and interaction with group.
3. How open minded is the individual.
4. Listening skill.
5. How are the views and idea put forward to the group

3. FACE TO FACE INTERVIEW

Making the students aware and prepare them for a few expected questions which will be asked in the interview is the smart work placement officer has to do in order to have more numbers of students placed out of the students appearing for interview.

TIPS REGARDING INTERVIEW AND THE ATTIRE

1. Research the potential employer
2. Review the job description and match your experience and education with the duties of the position
3. Prepare a 1 to 2 minute script about yourself.
4. Be sure to arrive 10 to 15 minutes prior to the start of the interview
5. Greet the interviewer with a firm handshake
6. Maintain good eye contact and posture

7. Make sure you are energetic and enthusiastic
8. Speak clearly and articulate

STANDARD INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

1. Would you tell me about yourself?
2. What is your greatest strength?
3. What is your greatest weakness?
4. Where do you see yourself in 5 years?
5. What about this position do you find most appealing?
6. Why do you want to work for our company?
7. Why should we hire you?

CONCLUSION

Today, new generation managers are expected to garnish soft skills along with the technical/hard skills. The modern corporate managers should have the talent to understand situations, fill in the missing conversations, capacity to connect and coordinate, and should know how to enlist the support from others. The ability to work in team and good interpersonal skills definitely add worth in the growth and promotion of corporate executive. The research results show that soft skills of the students can be refined if management colleges pass on the adequately framed and standardized soft skills training sessions to them. Students who are regularly exposed to soft skills sessions will have an edge over other students not only with respect to employability but also with respect to overall personality growth.

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